

Data-sharing as an epistemic practice - Taking the content of research seriously

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Abstract

To address a persistent theoretical gap in our sociological understanding of conditions for successful and sustainable sharing of research data, this contribution advocates for taking the content of research seriously when analysing data sharing practices. It reviews recent literature on data sharing with a particular focus on work from a science studies perspective that seeks to improve our understanding of data sharing as a social process that is part of the epistemic practices of research communities. It discusses current shortcomings in the analysis of field differences and how, besides institutional and individual-level factors, the specific ways in which knowledge is produced in different fields need to be considered in order to arrive at a comprehensive understanding of the potential of and conditions for the productive and sustainable sharing of research data.

1. Introduction

This contribution discusses what it means to understand the sharing of research data as an epistemic practice, a social practice that is embedded in the collective production of scientific knowledge in scientific communities. It starts from the assumption that productive and sustainable¹ data sharing is the end goal of open data initiatives, and that important insights can be drawn from studying existing patterns of data sharing and data re-use. This contribution reviews recent literature on data sharing with a particular focus on work from a science studies perspective that seeks to improve our understanding of data sharing as a social process that is part of the epistemic practices of research communities. The contribution assesses progress made and remaining knowledge gaps, and outlines a re-conceptualization of data sharing that results from taking the content of research seriously.

This move addresses in part the concern that while researchers have been found to widely support open science and the sharing of research data, in alignment with the Mertonian norm of communism (Merton 1973, p. 273-275), actual behaviors seem to diverge (Zhu 2020, Tenopir 2020, Nicholas et al. 2020, Fecher 2017), and non-sharing or withholding is common. Rather than casting the problem as a conflict between generic norms at the macro-level, and individual-level interests, it zooms in on the meso-level at which scientific communities integrate data sharing into their research practices. This happens to varying degrees in different fields (Velden & Tcypina 2023, Khan et al. 2023, Kim & Stanton 2016), pointing to the role of research practices and the content of research as a central factor for explaining patterns of sharing.

¹ Sustainable here means to have a balanced trade-off between the effort needed to achieve productive (not pro forma) sharing, and the benefits arrived at through the re-use of shared research data.

2. Recent Pushback on Openness

In recent years, the attention in science policy debates and infrastructure initiatives is largely focused on openness, and the public sharing of research data². However, some recent studies of the sharing of research data have started to push back on an exclusive focus on openness and emphasize the collaborative dimension of productive data sharing.

A recent interview-based study (Barlösius 2023) draws attention to forms of data sharing that are happening below the ‘open data’ radar. If one includes data sharing within research groups and within collaborative projects, then “far more data-sharing is happening in scientific practice than seems to be the case if one works only with the concept of open data” (ibid. p. 261). The study is explicitly not focused on the sharing of open data in anonymous and abstract social relationships, but on sharing data in ‘peer to peer relationships.’ Building on Max Weber’s characterization of social relationships as communal versus associative, and open versus closed, the author distinguishes three social forms of data sharing:

1. Closed communal sharing (including ‘raw’) data within research groups. It is a consequence of how research groups conduct research. It rests on a feeling of belonging and a shared subjective meaning of data sharing including the recognition and protection of the scientific achievement of the main data creators.
2. Closed associative sharing of (mostly ‘processed’) data with people outside of the research group for the purpose of joint research. It is instrumental in character and rests on a social process of finding an agreement on data sharing that adjusts researchers’ interests.
3. Open associative sharing of (‘final’) data may ensue after the data have become publicly visible, e.g. through presentations or posters at conferences or the publication of results based on the data. The rules for sharing are outside of the control of the data sharing scientists. This form of sharing is perceived by them as a “duty stemming from the binding character of a formally guaranteed framework of sharing” (ibid. p. 258).

Barlösius concludes her discussion of the sociality of data sharing by emphasizing how in all three cases, a social relationship exists or is created that underlies the data sharing, and “The specifics of this sociality **determine** why, how, and what data are shared.” (ibid. p. 260; emphasis in bold is mine). This is a remarkably strong statement, given the limited empirical basis of the study. The study’s findings derive from an analysis of 34 interviews with researchers from four disciplines (biology, computer science, linguistics, psychology) who are working in research groups in Germany, producing experimental data – a limitation in scope acknowledged by the author. In spite of the variation in fields, the focus on experimental data in combination with the fields selected reduces the variation in terms of epistemic practice and social structure of the communities involved. Consequently, we cannot know, how well the findings translate to other types of data than experimental data, or other types of scholarship that differ in their collaborative intensity (ranging from lone scholars, say in history or philosophy to large scale collaborations, say in high-energy physics) or in their dependence on research data generated outside of their own lab setting, such as in astronomy, ecology, or economics.

While we may need to exercise caution regarding the generalizability of the findings presented in Barlösius (2023), the analysis does provide an interesting theoretical framing from a sociological perspective of different forms of sociality underlying different forms of sharing. For example the personal sharing and bartering of research data between research groups described in earlier work (e.g. Hilgartner & Brandt-Rauf 1994, p. 163, Wallis et al. 2013) would

² Including allowances for making exceptions from public accessibility due to the sensitivity of data,

fall into the category of closed, associative sharing. Further, the finding that productive data sharing (namely sharing that leads to re-use) is oftentimes a collaborative endeavor that involves the data creator, aligns with other recent studies of data sharing.

The importance of collaborative data re-use that involves the data creator has been highlighted by Pasquetto et al. (2019). Based on a qualitative analysis of empirical data collected in two long-term observations of distributed consortia conducting interdisciplinary research, the authors suggest that there exists a continuum of types of data reuse, ranging from ‘comparative data reuse’ at one end to ‘integrative data reuse’ at the other (ibid., p.18). According to the authors, comparative data reuse, which serves to ground-truth one’s own research, through calibration, comparison, or confirmation is a rather routine occurrence in scientific practice. By contrast, integrative data reuse, which serves to conduct new analyses with the data, e.g. by combining it with other data is rare (ibid. p 24). Importantly, this type of data reuse requires much greater expertise in how the data were generated, can be used, and interpreted. For this reason, integrative data reuse is often conducted in collaboration with the original data creator.

Both studies provide important insights into data sharing as a social process. Preconditions for data sharing to succeed are not merely technical and a matter of providing infrastructural support for data sharing and open data. The social relationship and interactions between the researchers involved play a crucial role in enabling sharing and reuse of research data.

However, given the large variety in practices of knowledge production (Leonelli 2022), what is still missing, is a systematic analysis of how those social relationships are influenced by conditions that are specific to and arise from the way knowledge is produced within a scientific community.

3. Understanding Field Differences

The state of research on the influence of field-specific factors on the sharing of research data is still unsatisfactory. The large majority of research studies on data sharing, whether qualitative observational or interview studies, or quantitative studies using survey or bibliometric methods, focus on specific fields or research contexts. Especially qualitative, ethnographic case studies tend to emphasize the situatedness, complexity, and temporality of data sharing (e.g. Hilgartner 2012, Leonelli & Tempini 2020). Very few studies take a field-comparative approach in order to tease out how fields differ and how (among all other, social and institutional, factors to be taken into account) the specific way how knowledge is produced in a field, influences data sharing.

Observational and interview studies with an explicit, field-comparative design are extremely rare, likely due to the effort involved in acquiring the necessary ‘interactional’ expertise (Evans & Collins 2007) needed to study research and data sharing practices. Exceptions are represented e.g. by Taubert (2019, 2021), whose mixed-method based field-comparative study examines the adoptions of preprint sharing, not data sharing, in astronomy and mathematics, and Priego et al. (2022), whose field-comparative, qualitative case studies of two data infrastructures address the question what mechanisms may mitigate deterrents to data sharing in molecular biology and high energy physics. Notable in this context is the extensive, qualitative research program of Christine Borgman and colleagues on knowledge infrastructures (Borgman et al. 2021), who have for more than two decades conducted ethnographic studies of data sharing and reuse in different interdisciplinary research contexts and scientific fields from an information science perspective. This program is supported by in-depth empirical studies in specific fields or contexts, such as the dissertation research of

Wallis (2012) on data management in an NSF interdisciplinary research and technology center, of Sands on data management in astronomy (2017), and of Pasquetto (2018) on data sharing and re-use in bio-medicine. When examining these cases, the great variation in data types and data practices become evident (Borgman 2012), including the variation of data types and practices within fields (Darch & Sands 2015, Borgman 2015). The thrust of this research program has been to explore the variety in data practices and to identify what can be learned from and generalized across these diverse contexts in order to inform the development of knowledge infrastructures (Borgman & Bourne 2022, Pasquetto et al. 2019, p. 8).

Compared to qualitative, and in particular ethnographic, approaches, survey research more readily accomplishes a broad coverage of scientific fields. However, few survey studies adopt an explicit field-comparative design in order to examine the influence of field-specific research practices and conditions on sharing (see Tcypina 2024). Many data-sharing surveys focus on single fields or disciplines, and even when researchers from multiple fields are included, samples are highly skewed in terms of coverage of different fields, or fields are distinguished only at a rather coarse level (Fecher 2017, Tenopir 2011, 2015, State of Open Data Report Series, e.g. Digital Science et al. 2023), which undermines the ability to systematically analyze field differences that are due to differences in research practices (Velden & Tcypina 2023).

Hence, also among survey studies only few can be found that explicitly examine factors that may underlie field differences, such as the survey study by Kim & Stanton (2016) on post-publication data sharing, and the study by Thursby et al (2018) on the pre-publication disclosure of results (which may or may not involve research data). The latter study has identified competition as a field-level factor that is associated with field differences in rates of sharing, and both studies further identify sharing-supporting norms as a relevant field-level factor (Thursby et al. 2018, Kim & Stanton 2016). Both studies, however, provide only limited insight into how either competition or sharing norms are linked to a field's epistemic practices. Since neither the variation between fields in levels of competition, nor in sharing-supporting norms are self-explanatory, these findings underscore the need to examine more closely how such variations arise, and how decisions to share research data are embedded in the specific epistemic and social contexts of scientific communities.

4. Taking the content of research seriously

One way to illustrate the existing knowledge gap in the explanation of data sharing behaviors is to distinguish between a macro-level, meso-level, and micro-level perspective, each with a different focus on what factors influence decisions to share or withhold research data (table 1). For illustration, examples of studies are assigned to the level of analysis that corresponds to their focus and major thrust of argument.

The macro-level perspective focuses on factors that are generic for scientific knowledge production. For example the dependence of data sharing on institutional support, such as the availability of resources and infrastructures, or implementation of schemes that reward data sharing, e.g. in form of formalized data citations. I also include here studies that generalize across fields in order to identify principles that are generic for all fields of science, such as the three forms of sociality underlying peer-to-peer sharing distinguished by Barlösius (2023), or the 'data creator's advantage' highlighted by Pasquetto et al. (2019).

The micro-level perspective focuses on researchers as individuals and how individual-level characteristics may explain variation in sharing behaviors. Examples are studies of the influence of personality characteristics on sharing decisions (e.g. Linek et al. 2017) or of reputational orientation (e.g. Dorta-González et al. 2021).

The meso-level perspective focuses on the content of research as an influencing factor for sharing. It examines the influence of scientific communities and the ways they produce knowledge, on the sharing of research data. This accounts for epistemic practices as well as social structures of scientific communities, which are interlinked (Knorr-Cetina 1999, Whitley 2000). It further includes the variation in characteristics of the data produced, the diversity of which is highlighted e.g. by Borgman (2012).

Importantly, the meso-level influences factors at the macro-level (e.g. policies, infrastructures for sharing) or the micro-level (e.g. career benefits of sharing). This underlines the importance to develop a better understanding of the meso-level and how it influences sharing.

Table 1: Macro-level, meso-level, and micro-level perspectives on explaining variation in data sharing practices.

Analytical Perspective	Factors influencing sharing	Studies
Macro - <i>Science System</i>	Science Policy (mandates, funding)	Piwowar & Chapman (2010)
	Institutional Support (resources, infrastructure, reward)	van Gend & Zuiderwijk (2023), Kim (2017)
	Generic Features of Social Order of Knowledge Production (incl. Merton's norms of science)	Barlösius (2023) Pasquetto et al. (2019)
Meso - <i>Scientific communities</i>	Types of Data	Borgman (2012)
	Social structures of research fields	Thursby et al. (2018) Haas & Park (2010)
	Epistemic Properties of Research	Kim & Stanton (2016) Priego et al. (2022)
Micro - <i>Individuals</i>	Personality	Linek et al. (2017)
	Reputational orientation	Dorta-González (2021)
	Career stage, seniority	Tenopir et al. (2011)

Often, studies in the data sharing domain touch on several of these levels. For example, survey studies often collect information about institutional and policy aspects, individual characteristics and attitudes, field affiliation and, possibly, types of data. However, if the

meso-level is neglected in the analysis, conclusions about the drivers of sharing remain incomplete.

To illustrate this point: a survey-based study by Kim & Zhang (2015) of 1,298 researchers in STEM³ disciplines tested a structural model that suggests individual-level motivations (relating to perceived career benefits and risks, and perceived effort), along with resource factors (data repository availability) and normative pressure, influence data sharing attitudes and behaviors. Supported by the statistical evaluation of the hypothesized model, they point to the critical role of infrastructure availability for actual data sharing behavior: “This finding supports the argument that data repositories can [...] facilitate STEM researchers’ data sharing behaviors.” While the analysis, building on the theory of planned behavior, elucidates how individual level perceptions of risks and benefits, availability of infrastructures, and perception of the disciplinary norms in a field may all influence data sharing behaviors, arguably the elephant in the room is the underlying causality that is not touched upon: namely those meso-level epistemic factors that have spurred the emergence of data repositories in the first place, and the evolution of disciplinary norms in support of data sharing.

The point made here is that more research effort needs to be spent on understanding the causal influence of the middle layer, of how the sharing of research data is not only influenced by the specific ways of knowledge production in scientific communities, but an expression of the specific ways of knowledge production in scientific communities. If we define epistemic practices as “Typical (repeatedly occurring) actions of members of scientific communities that are aimed at the production of contributions to the community’s knowledge.” (Gläser & Franssen, *forthcoming*), then productive forms of research data sharing constitute epistemic practices in their own right.

The call to not reduce sharing of research data to a social act within the binary relationship of individual researchers, but “to pay especially close attention to the way particular inputs and outputs are embedded in evolving streams of scientific production.” has been made by Hilgartner & Brandt-Rauf (1994, p. 158), already 30 years ago in their seminal paper on data access, introducing the data streams concept to articulate the complexity of research data as it evolves and changes through the data production and analysis process⁴.

What is needed to further develop the theoretical understanding of the variation of data sharing at the meso-level, is twofold: On the one hand, given the diversity of fields and epistemic practices we need further thorough case studies of research communities and their practices, including studies that can provide deep insights into the historical evolution of practices, infrastructures, and policies of data sharing (such as Strasser 2019, Hilgartner 2017, and Kohler 1994). However, while insightful and instructive, such in-depth case studies mould their analytical framework towards the specific case they are treating. Hence what is needed on the other hand are comparative studies, that not only take the content of research seriously, but further develop a systematic approach towards field comparisons in order to examine how the production, sharing and (re)use of data as an epistemic practice differs between fields.

³ Acronym for Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics.

⁴ Hilgartner in his own long-term empirical work followed through by studying processes of granting, limiting, or denying access to data and other forms of knowledge in the field of genomics, culminating in a book titled ‘*Reordering life: Knowledge and control in the genomics revolution*’ (Hilgartner 2017).

So far, very little is known about the function that sharing data has in scientific knowledge production (in what ways it advances knowledge production) and how these functions vary across epistemic contexts. For example, the function of sharing and perceived value of sharing a specific type of data with other researchers (see e.g. Akmon 2014, Priego et al. 2022) can be expected to influence decisions to share and to be connected to the emergence of respective sharing supporting norms.

Hence future, field-comparative research needs to address:

- How sharing of research data advances the production of knowledge in different research fields;
- How variation in sharing supporting norms and competition dynamics arise from differences in epistemic properties of research and affect researchers' decisions to share;
- What social mechanisms (Gläser & Laudel 2019) can be identified and tested that provide causal explanations of the empirically observed meso-level differences in rates and forms of sharing.

Only by addressing these open questions, we will be able to close the theoretical gap in our understanding of the potential of and conditions for successful and sustainable sharing of research data.

From a methodological perspective, such comparative studies will likely benefit from and require combining qualitative research such as observations and semi-structured interviews that can provide insights into causal mechanisms, and quantitative research, using survey, bibliometric, and text-analytic approaches to establish and quantify the empirical prevalence of relevant factors and data sharing outcomes, and confirm the correlation, or 'difference making relationship' between relevant factors (Ghiara 2022).

5. Conclusion

Important progress has been made in understanding the question of data sharing and open data not only as a technical question, but a social question as well. The point made here is that a social process, such as the sharing of research data, is not only influenced by social factors at the macro- and the micro level, but also by epistemic and socio-structural factors that vary at a meso-level of analysis of scientific practices. To account for the strong variation between research specialties in how they produce knowledge, we need to study the embedding of data sharing into epistemic practices and the function of data sharing in the collective knowledge production of scientific communities. In particular, more work needs to be done to examine and articulate the linkages between epistemic conditions of research and the social structures and interdependencies between researchers that influence decisions to share. To study such meso-level variations and underlying causation systematically, a comparative approach is needed.

Open science practices

As a conceptual paper there are no empirical data or data analysis methods to be shared.

Competing interests

No competing interests.

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